

Optimized Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) with Enhanced S-Box and Automated Key Generation

Dr. D Naga Ravikiran, R V Prasanth Reddy, N Prasanthi Rani, P Ajay Kumar, Venkata Siva Sai Teja

Department of Electronics and Communications Engineering, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Mothadaka, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India.

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KEYWORDS

AES,
S-box Optimization,
Composite Field Arithmetic,
FPGA Implementation

ABSTRACT

The Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is a widely used encryption algorithm crucial for ensuring data security. One of its key components, the Substitution Box (S-box), enhances security by introducing confusion and diffusion during encryption. However, conventional S-box implementations using Look-Up Tables (LUTs) or embedded memory often introduce significant path delay overhead and are vulnerable to cryptographic attacks. This paper presents an optimized composite field arithmetic-based approach for Sub-bytes and Inverse Sub-bytes operations, addressing these challenges. The proposed design integrates higher-order transformations and inner-stage pipelining schemes, improving throughput and reducing latency. The AES cryptosystem is implemented using VHDL and synthesized with the Xilinx ISE tool, demonstrating an efficient, hardware-optimized encryption model. This approach enhances both performance and security, making it a viable solution for real-time cryptographic applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Data Encryption Standard (DES) was initially adopted as the standard for symmetric key encryption. However, with a key length of only 56 bits, DES became increasingly vulnerable to brute-force attacks due to advancements in computational power. Recognizing the need for a more secure encryption algorithm, the

National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) initiated a formal selection process in September 1997 to establish a new encryption standard.

In August 1998, fifteen candidate algorithms were introduced, and an extensive evaluation was conducted by cryptographic researchers worldwide. By August 2000, five algorithms—Mars, RC6, Rijndael, Serpent, and

Twofish—were shortlisted for further analysis. After rigorous assessment, Rijndael was officially selected as the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) on October 2, 2000. AES supports flexible key and block sizes, operating in multiples of 32 bits, with key sizes of 128, 192, or 256 bits. This adaptability significantly enhances security, making key-breaking computationally infeasible.

AES can be efficiently implemented in both hardware and software. While software-based implementations require minimal resources, they often lack physical security and have lower processing speeds. To meet the increasing demand for high-speed and high-volume secure communication, hardware implementations have become more prevalent. Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) offer an optimal balance between General-Purpose Processors (GPPs) and Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs), delivering faster processing speeds, reconfigurability, and wider applicability across various domains.

Since its official adoption in 2001, AES has become the global standard for encryption, playing a crucial role in internet banking, secure communication protocols, and embedded security applications. Depending on the use case, AES implementations vary in terms of speed, power consumption, and hardware constraints. As a result, AES is deployed across multiple platforms, from general-purpose software-based systems to high-speed, energy-efficient hardware solutions that ensure enhanced security with minimal computational overhead.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) has been extensively studied and implemented in various ways to enhance security, efficiency, and performance. Researchers have explored different optimization techniques, including S-box improvements, key management strategies, and hardware acceleration, to strengthen AES encryption. This section reviews significant contributions in these areas.

Optimization of AES S-Box:

The AES S-box is a crucial component responsible for the non-linearity in the encryption process, significantly influencing security and computational efficiency. Various studies have aimed to optimize its implementation:

- Hasan&Jubadi (2010) proposed a combinational logic-based S-box to reduce delay and improve security by minimizing vulnerabilities associated with Look-Up Table (LUT) implementations.
- Ahmad et al. (2011) designed an AES S-box optimized for FPGA implementation using a composite field approach, significantly improving hardware efficiency and reducing power consumption.

These studies demonstrate that replacing the traditional LUT-based S-box with a composite field arithmetic approach enhances performance while maintaining high security.

Secure Key Management in AES:

Key management plays a pivotal role in AES security, as traditional methods relying on manually entered keys are prone to leakage and compromise.

- Borkar et al. (2011) implemented AES using biometric-based key generation, which enhances security by eliminating manual key entry and mitigating key leakage risks.
- Trang Hoang & Van Loi Nguyen (2012) introduced an AES design with dynamic key expansion, ensuring that encryption keys are less predictable and resistant to cryptographic attacks.

These advancements indicate that automated or biometric key generation significantly strengthens AES security compared to conventional key management techniques.

Hardware-Based AES Implementations:

Given the increasing demand for high-speed encryption in real-time applications, researchers have explored AES implementations on hardware platforms such as Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) and Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs).

- Tessier& Burtleson (2001) reviewed FPGA-based AES implementations and concluded that FPGAs provide a good trade-off between speed, flexibility, and cost for cryptographic applications.
- Panato et al. (2002) presented an AES Intellectual Property (IP) core optimized for Altera devices, achieving low latency and high throughput.

These studies confirm that hardware-based AES implementations offer better performance and security

compared to software implementations, making them suitable for high-performance encryption applications.

FPGA-Based AES Design and Optimization:

Recent advancements in FPGA-based AES implementations focus on reducing hardware complexity, power consumption, and execution time.

- Venkateswarlu et al. (2015) developed an AES implementation on Spartan 3E FPGA, optimizing memory usage and execution speed for real-time encryption applications.
- Hoang & Nguyen (2018) introduced a pipelined AES architecture, enabling high-speed encryption with minimal hardware overhead.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

AES ALGORITHM

The AES algorithm is a symmetric block cipher that can encrypt and decrypt information. Encryption converts data to an unintelligible form called cipher-text. Decryption of the cipher-text converts the data back into its original form, which is called plain-text.

AES ENCRYPTION

The AES algorithm operates on a 128-bit block of data and executed $Nr - 1$ loop times. A loop is called a round and the number of iterations of a loop, Nr , can be 10, 12, or 14 depending on the key length. The key length is 128, 192 or 256 bits in length respectively. The first and last rounds differ from other rounds in that there is an additional Add Round Key transformation at the beginning of the first round and no Mix Columns transformation is performed in the last round. In this paper, we use the key length of 128 bits (AES-128) as a model for general explanation. An outline of AES encryption is given in Fig 3.1.

SUBBYTES TRANSFORMATION

The SubBytes transformation is a non-linear byte substitution, operating on each of the state bytes independently. The SubBytes transformation is done using a once- pre-calculated substitution table called S box. That S-box table contains 256 numbers (from 0 to 255) and their corresponding resulting values. More details of the method of calculating the S-box table. In this design, we use a look-up table as shown in Table 3.1. This is a more efficient method than directly implementing the multiplicative inverse operation

followed by affine transformation. This approach avoids complexity of hardware implementation and has the significant advantage of performing the S-box computation in a single clock cycle, thus reducing the latency.

Figure 1: AES encryption structure

Table: 1 S-BOX TABLE

		Y															
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	a	b	c	d	e	f
X	0	63	7c	77	7b	f2	6b	6f	c5	30	1	67	2b	fe	d7	ab	76
	1	ca	82	c9	7d	fa	59	47	f0	ad	d4	a2	af	9c	a4	72	c0
	2	b7	fd	93	26	36	3f	f7	cc	34	a5	e5	f1	71	d8	31	15
	3	4	c7	23	c3	18	96	5	9a	7	12	80	e2	eb	27	b2	75
	4	9	83	2c	1a	1b	6e	5a	a0	52	3b	d6	b3	29	e3	2f	84
	5	53	d1	0	ed	20	fc	b1	5b	6a	cb	be	39	4a	4c	58	cf
	6	d0	ef	aa	fb	43	4d	33	85	45	f9	2	7f	50	3c	9f	a8
	7	51	a3	40	8f	92	9d	38	f5	bc	b6	da	21	10	ff	f3	d2
	8	cd	0c	13	ec	5f	97	44	17	c4	a7	7e	3d	64	5d	19	73
	9	60	81	4f	dc	22	2a	90	88	46	ee	b8	14	de	5e	0b	db
	a	e0	32	3a	0a	49	6	24	5c	c2	d3	ac	62	91	95	e4	79
	b	e7	c8	37	6d	8d	d5	4e	a9	6c	56	f4	ea	65	7a	ae	8
	c	ba	78	25	2e	1c	a6	b4	c6	e8	dd	74	1f	4b	bd	8b	8a
	d	70	3e	b5	66	48	3	f6	0e	61	35	57	b9	86	c1	1d	9e
	e	e1	f8	98	11	69	d9	8e	94	9b	1e	87	e9	ce	55	28	df
	f	8c	a1	89	0d	bf	e6	42	68	41	99	2d	0f	b0	54	bb	16

SHIFTRAWS TRANSFORMATION

In ShiftRows transformation, the rows of the state are cyclically left shifted over different offsets. Row 0 is not

shifted; row 1 is shifted one byte to the left; row 2 is shifted two bytes to the left and row 3 is shifted three bytes to the left.

The ShiftRows step is a byte transposition that cyclically shifts the rows of the state over different offsets. Row 0 is shifted over C_0 bytes, row 1 over C_1 bytes, row 2 over C_2 bytes and row 3 over C_3 bytes, so that the byte at position j in row i moves to position $(j - C_i) \bmod N_b$. The shift offsets C_0, C_1, C_2 and C_3 depend on the value of N_b .

Design criteria for the offsets The design criteria for the offsets are the following:

1. **Diffusion optimal.** The four offsets have to be different.
2. **Other diffusion effects.** The resistance against truncated differential attacks and saturation attacks has to be maximized.

Diffusion optimality is important in providing resistance against differential and linear cryptanalysis. The other diffusion effects are only relevant when the block length is larger than 128 bits.

Selection of the offsets. The simplicity criterion dictates that one offset is taken equal to 0. In fact, for a block length of 128 bits, the offsets have to be 0, 1, 2 and 3. The assignment of offsets to rows is arbitrary. For block lengths larger than 128 bit, there are more possibilities. Detailed studies of truncated differential attacks and saturation attacks on reduced versions of Rijndael show that not all choices are equivalent. For certain choices, the attacks can be extended with one round. Among the choices that are best with respect to saturation and truncated differential attacks, we picked the simplest ones. Different values are specified in Table 2. Figure 2 illustrate the effect of the ShiftRows step on the state. Figure 3 shows the pictograms for ShiftRows and its inverse.

Table 2 ShiftRows: shift offsets for different block lengths

N_b	C_0	C_1	C_2	C_3
4	0	1	2	3
5	0	1	2	3
6	0	1	2	3
7	0	1	2	4
8	0	1	3	4

Figure 2: ShiftRows operates on the rows of the state

Figure 3: Pictograms for ShiftRows (left) and InvShiftRows (right)

The inverse operation of ShiftRows is called InvShiftRows. It is a cyclic shift of the 3 bottom rows over $N_b - C_1, N_b - C_2$ and $N_b - C_3$ bytes respectively so that the byte at position j in row i moves to position $(j + C_i) \bmod N_b$.

MIXCOLUMNS TRANSFORMATION

In Mix Columns transformation, the columns of the state are considered as polynomials over $GF(2^8)$ and multiplied by modulo $x^4 + 1$ with a fixed polynomial $c(x)$, given by: $c(x) = \{03\}x^3 + \{01\}x^2 + \{01\}x + \{02\}$.

The MixColumns step is a bricklayer permutation operating on the state column by column.

Design criteria: The design criteria for the MixColumns step are the following:

1. **Dimensions.** The transformation is a bricklayer transformation operating on 4 byte columns.
2. **Linearity.** The transformation is preferably linear over $GF(2)$.
3. **Diffusion.** The transformation has to have relevant diffusion power.
4. **Performance on 8-bit processors.** The performance of the transformation on 8-bit processors has to be high.

The criteria about linearity and diffusion are requirements imposed by the wide trail strategy. The dimensions criterion of having columns consisting of 4 bytes is to make optimal use of 32-bit architectures in look-up table implementations. The performance on 8-bit processors is mentioned because MixColumns is the only step that good performance on 8-bit processors is not trivial to obtain for.

ADD ROUND KEY TRANSFORMATION

In the AddRoundKey transformation, a RoundKey is added to the State - resulted from the operation of the MixColumns transformation - by a simple bitwise XOR operation. The RoundKey of each round is derived from the main key using the Key Expansion algorithm. The encryption/decryption algorithm needs eleven 128-bit RoundKey, which are denoted RoundKey(the first RoundKey is the main key).

The round transformation is denoted Round, and is a sequence of four transformations, called steps. This is shown in List below. The final round of the cipher is slightly different. It is denoted Final Round and also shown in List below. In the listings, the transformations (Round, SubBytes, ShiftRows, . . .) operate on arrays to which pointers (State, Expanded Key [i]) are provided. It is easy to verify that the transformation Final Round is equal to the transformation Round, but with the MixColumns step removed. The steps are specified in the following subsections, together with the design criteria we used for each step. Besides the step-specific criteria, we also applied the following two general design criteria.

AES DECRYPTION

Decryption is a reverse of encryption which inverse round transformations to computes out the original plaintext of an encrypted cipher-text in reverse order. The round transformation of decryption uses the functions AddRoundKey, InvMixColumns, InvShiftRows, and InvSubBytes successively.

ADDDROUNDKEY

AddRoundKey is its own inverse function because the XOR function is its own inverse. The round keys have to be selected in reverse order. The description of the other transformations will be given as follows.

INVSHIFTRROWS TRANSFORMATION

InvShiftRows exactly functions the same as ShiftRows, only in the opposite direction. The first row is not shifted, while the second, third and fourth rows are shifted right by one, two and three bytes respectively.

INVSUBBYTES TRANSFORMATION

The InvSubBytes transformation is done using a once-precalculated substitution table called InvS-box. That InvS-box table contains 256 numbers (from 0 to 255) and their corresponding values. InvS-box is presented in Table 3.3.

Table 3:INVS-BOX TABLE

		Y															
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	a	b	c	d	e	f
X	0	52	9	6a	d5	30	36	a5	38	bf	40	a3	9e	81	f3	d7	fb
	1	7c	e3	39	82	9b	2f	ff	87	34	8e	43	44	c4	de	e9	cb
	2	54	7b	94	32	a6	c2	23	3d	ee	4c	95	0b	42	fa	c3	4e
	3	e	2e	a1	66	28	d9	24	b2	76	5b	a2	49	6d	8b	d1	25
	4	72	f8	f6	64	86	68	98	16	d4	a4	5c	cc	5d	65	b6	92
	5	6c	70	48	50	fd	ed	b9	da	5e	15	46	57	a7	8d	9d	84
	6	90	d8	ab	0	8c	bc	d3	0a	f7	e4	58	5	b8	b3	45	6
	7	d0	2c	1e	8f	ca	3f	0f	2	c1	af	bd	3	1	13	8a	6b
	8	3a	91	11	41	4f	67	dc	ea	97	f2	cf	ce	f0	b4	e6	73
	9	96	ac	74	22	e7	ad	35	85	e2	f9	37	e8	1c	75	df	6e
	a	47	f1	1a	71	1d	29	c5	89	6f	b7	62	0e	aa	18	be	1a
	b	fc	56	3e	4b	c6	d2	79	20	9a	db	c0	fe	78	cd	5a	f4
	c	1f	dd	a8	33	88	7	c7	31	b1	12	10	59	27	80	ec	5f
	d	60	51	7f	a9	19	b5	4a	0d	2d	e5	7a	9f	93	c9	9c	ef
	e	a0	e0	3b	4d	ae	2a	f5	b0	c8	eb	bb	3c	83	53	99	61
	f	17	2b	4	7e	ba	77	d6	26	e1	69	14	63	55	21	0c	7d

INVMIXCOLUMNS TRANSFORMATION

In the InvMixColumns transformation, the polynomials of degree less than 4 over GF(2⁸), which coefficients are the elements in the columns of the state, are multiplied modulo (x⁴+ 1) by a fixed polynomial d(x) = {0B}x³ + {0D}x² + {09}x +{0E}, where {0B}, {0D}; {09}, {0E} denote hexadecimal values. In the next section, a description of the proposed design based on FPGA implementation of AES encryption/decryption function is detailed.

In this work, we have used S-box using composite field algorithm, which contains sub-bytes and inverse sub-bytes operation. Both these modules can use encryption and decryption in a shared way which requires less hardware. These blocks used successive XOR operations and transformed the value into some other values . It consists of various sub-modules like affine transformation, multiplication inverse, and multiplication with constant. Composite S-box

implementation is the fastest and safer method to implement.

Figure 4: Composite S-box with non-linear transformation

It requires the text_in, text_out and key which have a 128 bits length. And the control signals using to control the proper operations of the core are clk, reset_n, write, direction, done and enable pins. The Key block loads keys and combines with Key Round block to perform Key Expansion transformation, and generates proper Roundkeys under the control signals from the Controller block. Controller block takes write signal, direction signal, and enable signal from outside and generates all the control signals for the whole system. The plain text (text_in) and key is loaded only when the write signal makes a low-high-low transition (basically a pulse). The process is going to complete when the done signal is pulsed after some clock cycles from the write signal goes low. The "done" signal actives only in one clock cycle.

Each round key as well as round is completed in one clock cycle. However, the round key is finished before the round is calculated by one clock cycle. Hence, combining with one clock cycle for registering the input, a total clock cycle need for processing 128-bit data is 13 clocks in encryption mode. In decryption, eleven round keys must be completed before the first round is calculated. Because the last round key is used in the first round process, it takes 25 clock cycles to complete. With using the above iterative looping approach, a minimal number of clock cycles required performing encryption/decryption for each data block of 128-bit.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION SIMULATION RESULT

Figure 5: Simulation result of encryption

Figure 5 shows the output of encryption. Here the input is given as plain text of 128 bits and key length as 256 bits it generates output cipher text as 128 bits.

Figure 6: Simulation result of decryption

Figure 6 shows the output of encryption. Here the input is given as cipher text of 128 bits and key length as 256 bits it generates output plain text as 128 bits.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Figure 7: Block diagram of encryption

Figure 8: Block diagram of decryption

RTL:

Figure 9: RTL of encryption

Figure 10: RTL of decryption

TECHNOLOGY:

Figure 11: Technology description of encryption

Figure 12: Technology description of decryption

5.CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) algorithm, one of the most widely used encryption techniques, has been successfully designed and simulated using VHDL. The proposed architecture enhances security by utilizing a digital biometric key instead of the conventional manually entered key, thereby addressing key management and leakage concerns. Additionally, the optimized S-box implementation reduces hardware requirements by eliminating the need for hardcore block RAM. As a future enhancement, the design can be implemented on a Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) to further improve efficiency and performance.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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